

INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL CONFLICTS IN THE FORMATION OF CHARACTER

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Abstract: *The article is about the psychological inner world of the heroes in “Kidnapped” by R.L. Stevenson and “Oliver Twist” by Charles Dickens. It discusses types of individual’s psychological world which are the essential component of these novels. Both of these novels depict the life of boys who experienced problems in their life. They had individual principles of psychology which gives clear examples of personality. Writers described their heroes David and Oliver Twist to be strong and mighty teens who coped with the difficulties in society. They could find the most correct way of living in their life. Our approach towards these characters shows that psychoanalysis is based on the social conditions.*

Keywords: *psychology, conflict, goodness, creativity, internal, external, bullying, humiliation, descriptive analysis, humanity, challenges, endure.*

INTRODUCTION. “Oliver Twist” is a realistic novel which was written by Charles Dickens during Industrial Revolution. The writer wanted to show the dark history which he witnessed himself. There was a powerful class who dominated the whole society with its power. This upper class exploited the poor and used them for their own benefits. The exploitation was made over orphans who were abandoned alone without parents.

One member of those orphans was Oliver Twist who faced obstacles in his life. He experienced humiliation, bullying of despicable people and he could not fight against them because of his lack of strength and power. Sometimes the hero’s attitude towards those humiliations seemed aggressive for a reader. But the boy’s inner world was covered with the kindness which could help him to find prosperous destiny for himself.

Furthermore, the issues of crime through the portrayal of petty pickpockets, thieves’ life conditions were revealed in “Oliver Twist”. By revealing the vices of society the writer wanted to find solutions to the obstacles in life.

METHODOLOGY.

Comparative analysis – the strengths and weaknesses of the protagonist in “Kidnapped” by R.L. Stevenson can be seen in his actions to solve the problems of his life. There were small slugs on the island: in Scotland they were called "buckies"; and English people called them "minors." That's what David accepted, the "food" consisted of "buckies," and he would swallow them alive and cold: because he was as hungry as a horse.

The protagonist’s attitude to the social environment was positive. For example, we can see David’s close relationship with Alan Breck, a descendant of the Stewarts; he conspired with Alan against pirates on the ship. Consequently, David considered his close friend as his own brother. He gave the silver buttons which were given by his uncle to his friend as a gift; his positive behavior showed that the protagonist was being grown-up as a kind person in society.

Creativeness – the main goal of the writer is to show the creativity of the protagonist. *"I had to endure all the hardships," he said. Dizziness, nausea, and tingling in the joints in cold and moist weather exhausted my whole body. I used to repeat two verses from a Scottish religious song. I can't sleep at night, The sun does not shine during the day"* [163].

David's ability to control his anger and rage temporarily changed; he felt a scorn towards his close friend and he called him to a duel in chapter 24. But the grateful kindness of Alan to David evoked the boy's love towards his friend.

The hero's psyche was reflected in his ability to fight against internal and external world *"Kidnapped"*. This can be taken as internal and external conflicts in English. The internal conflict was that the protagonist was able to deal with all the hardships to survive on the island; The external conflict is David's struggle with the other characters in the novel. For example, he reclaimed his inheritance from his uncle Ebenezer. Furthermore, the writer used literary means of like simile and personification in order to convey some meanings. Simile: the writer used simile when describing the mood of the protagonist, *"I express my gratitude coldly. Stevenson compared his gratitude to the cold ice. "I do very well. I thank you as cold as ice". Personification: human qualities were transferred into animals and objects while describing David's solitude in isolated island. "I must lie down and die on these wet mountains, like a sheep or a fox and my bones must whiten there like the bones of beast" [1. p.175].*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

It's noticeably crucial to define the psychology of heroes in the novel of R.L. Stevenson's *"Kidnapped"*. Having heard that the protagonist of *"Kidnapped"* David Belfour, had an uncle he set out for travelling. The house belonged to him in Shaws Castle after his father's death. He met his uncle Ebenezer Belfour, whom he had never seen in Shaws Castle. But his uncle Ebenezer was not happy to see his nephew. As a result, he deliberately sent David to the dangerous part of the castle to kill him. When he couldn't manage with killing the child, he sold him. Thus, the novel unfolded and David Belfour appeared as a person in society. Using the method of descriptive analysis, the writer Robert Lewis Stevenson depicted skillfully the psychology of the protagonist as he experienced the challenges of life. David had to overcome many the hurdles of life in order to realize himself as a human being. Humanity is a conscious being. David's courage and bravery were represented by his ability to withstand any trials of life. These qualities were evident in his fighting against the pirates: *"... fear was replaced by courage, and I shot him (the pirate Batman) in the abdomen until I screamed at the top of my voice. He slipped through the hole and landed on his partner, who was lying down. It was impossible not to point a pistol, but there was no opportunity to do anything: I hit the barrel with the pistol ..."* [p. 78].

We can analyze Oliver Twist's psychology in Charles Dickens's novel *"Oliver Twist"*. In the novel, the Stevenson portrayed the protagonist, Oliver Twist, as a flawless, polite, sweet, benevolent hero by nature. Oliver's individual psychological condition was manifested in his ability to withstand any humiliation in society, we can notice these humiliations in several ways in the novel:

1. Physical bullying of the protagonist: The owner of a workhouse Mr. Bumble who took the advantage over the labor of young children, the child had endured bullying for nine years at workhouse. From the moment he was born, Oliver was wrapped in an old sheet. *"The young Oliver Twist was a wonderful baby with the power of dress, wrapped in a blanket that had formed his only covering so far, he could have been a nobleman or a beggar child, it would have been difficult to appoint him a*

*proud stranger to his worthy position in society. But now, when he was wrapped in old yellowed shirts with the same service, it was obviously known that and he was ticketed and fell immediately into the place - a church child - an orphan of the workhouse - a humble, half-starved drudge-to be cuffed and buffeted through the world- despised by all, and pitied by none”.*¹

2. Social humiliation of the protagonist: In the nineteenth century, poverty was rampant in London, and the lower classes were exploited by the upper classes. At the same time, there were groups of petty crimes in the society. They would steal things and give the stolen things to their masters. One of them was Fegin. He taught young teenagers how to steal things and earn their living in life. Oliver reluctantly came to this environment of thieves. Fegin forced him to steal things from people. As a result, the child was forced to live in the environment of thieves and he was locked in the house. He tried to escape from the thieves several times.

3. Verbal humiliation: Firstly, the bullying of Noah Claypol made Oliver more aggressive than the other characters in the novel. Noah Claypol insulted the boy’s mother. He was beaten by Oliver “*Oliver, blushing with rage, jumped up and overturned the table and chair, seized Noah by his throat, and shook him so hard that the asshole’s teeth chattered, and then, gathering all his strength in his fist, he defied him with an energy he had never known before”.*²

Secondly, verbal bullying occurred when Oliver asked for an extra bowl of porridge from Mr. Bumble. Punishing the poor boy Mr. Bumble poured cold water over the boy, and begged God to forgive his sins. Oliver Twist’s mental state was reflected in the following scenes: a) the ability of the protagonist to be creative can be observed in the fact that he used to escape from the group of thieves and he strived for the goodness in order to fulfill his dreams; b) the weakness of the protagonist was that he could not fight the cruel people who treated him badly; c) he was a sociable young boy like a nice gentleman in society – he could make good relationship with good people and he enjoyed being in a good environment. At the end of the novel, an orphaned child found a new way for his future. He found a good nice gentleman Mr. Branlow who accepted him as his son and a loving sister like Rose. Finally, Oliver could face happy future in his life.

CONCLUSION.

Both of the novels “*Kidnapped*” by R.L. Stevenson and “*Oliver Twist*” by Charles Dickens depict the life of boys who experienced problems in their life. They had individual principles of psychology which gives clear examples of personality. Writers described their heroes David and Oliver Twist to be strong and mighty teens who coped with the difficulties in society. They could find the most correct way of living in their life. Our approach towards these characters shows that psychoanalysis is based on the social conditions. Human nature is complicated. The nature of humanity is revealed through these social conditions. The impact of social conditions helps characters to reveal their psychological world. Literature serves as a tangible instrument for psychoanalysis of characters. Psychology, human mind, spirit of characters is the major principles of literature. Literature teaches people a lot of things that help them to find answers to their questions. To give a conclusion to our analysis we would prefer to illustrate the following table:

№	Stage	Oliver Twist	David Balfour
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¹ Ch. Dickens, “*Oliver Twist*”//the edition includes a Foreword, Biographical Note, and Afterword by Nancy Springer, 1998. – P. 6

² Ch. Dickens, “*Oliver Twist*”//the edition includes a Foreword, Biographical Note, and Afterword by Nancy Springer, 1998. – P. 8.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-6, ISSUE-3

1.	Start	Very Low	Neutral
		Orphan, poverty	Leaves home
2.	Conflict	(Low) workhouse abuse	(Very low) uncle's betrayal
3.	Struggle	thieves (Fagin)	kidnapped, survival
4.	Growth	escapes, meets kindness	friendship, courage
5.	Resolution	adoption, happiness	identity, inheritance

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